

BIOCHEMISTRY OF VITAMIN E

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ABSTRACT

In the last 20-30 years, interest in antioxidant substances, especially natural synthesis, has increased. Also, a deeper study of vitamins better reveals the biochemical and physiological aspects of the life of the cell and the extracellular matrix. Progress in science creates new flagogens that the human body has not encountered before. This leads to an increase in allergic reactions and chronic inflammation. Chronic inflammation itself can serve as a good breeding ground for the formation of tumors. Vitamin E analyzed in this work has a strong antioxidant effect [1], anti-inflammatory effect [2], and antitumor effect [3]. Given such important properties of tocopherols and tocotrienols, it would be correct to say that a medical professional should have an idea of what foods to find natural vitamin E in, what it is for, and what diseases can be prevented using supplements containing vitamin E.

Key words: Vitamin E, tocopherol, tocotrienol, chromal ring, chylomicrons, lipids, receptors, lipoproteins, affinity, flagogen, alteration, exudation, proliferation, prostaglandins, leukotrienes, cytokines, interleukins.

INTRODUCTION

Classification of Vitamin E: Vitamin E is a lipophilic substance. The vitamin E group includes 8 molecules α -, β -, γ -, δ -tocopherol (α T, β T, γ T, δ T) and α -, β -, γ -, δ -tocotrienol (α TE, β TE, γ TE, δ TE). All forms of vitamin E have a chromic ring and a 16-carbon chain. Tocopherols are saturated, and tocotrienols have three double bonds. Also, tocopherols and tocotrienols are distinguished by the 5th or 7th position of the chromanol ring by either the -H group or the -CH₃ group. Natural tocopherols have an RRR configuration in the 2, 4' and 8' positions, and tocotrienols have an R- configuration in 2nd position.

Natural forms of vitamin E are produced by plants [4]. Plant seeds like nuts are a rich source of α T and γ T. Widely consumed sunflower seeds in the form of seeds or butter almonds, and peanuts contain a lot of α T, and foods such as walnuts,

pistachios and sesame seeds contain γ T [5]. A sufficient amount of δ T is found in tomato seeds, rice germ and soybean oil. Tocotrienols, relative to tocopherols, are much less abundant in nuts and can be obtained from palm oil, barley and some grains.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The different isoforms of vitamin E are not equally distributed in our body. It has been found that the concentration of α T in plasma in people who do not receive additional vitamin complexes ranges from 20-30 μ M, while γ T can be 5-10 times lower than α T in the blood [1]. This difference is due to the different affinity between vitamin E isoforms and transport proteins or enzymes of tocopherols and tocotrienols.

Metabolism of vitamin E: Entering the small intestine with food, tocopherols and tocotrienols are absorbed along with lipids and are part of chylomicron particles along with triacylglycerins, phospholipids, fatty acids, cholesterol and other fat-soluble substances [1]. By binding to chylomicrons through the lymphatic system, vitamin E is delivered to all tissues and organs, in particular muscles, bone marrow, adipose tissue, skin and brain. Transport between tissues and chylomicrons most likely involves lipoprotein receptors, but these mechanisms are currently poorly understood. It is interesting to note that in these tissues the concentration of γ T. higher than α T. Unabsorbed remnants of vitamin E are delivered along with other molecules in the chylomicron to the liver and are absorbed there. In the liver, α T binds to the α -TTP transporter protein.

α -TTP together with ATP-binding cassette transporter A1 (ABCA1) [6] and incorporates α T with lipoproteins [1]. The α -TTP transporter protein has 100% affinity for α T, 50% for β T, 1-30% for γ T and δ T. The transporter protein also protects various forms of vitamin E from catabolism in the liver. So α T is 100% protected from enzymes due to its binding to protein. Other non-alpha forms in the liver are hydroxylated and oxidized by cytochrome P450, and in the second stage the β -oxidation of the phytol chain to 13'-hydroxychromanol occurs, but with high vitamin E intake the final metabolite may change.

Regulation of vitamin E metabolism: According to the works of Manor D. and Morley S. [6], it becomes clear that the main role in the regulation of metabolism belongs to the α -TTP transporter protein and ω -vitamin E hydroxylase. These proteins have, one might say, antagonistic properties. Thus, α -TTP prevents the catabolism of various isoforms, and ω -hydroxylase, on the

contrary, promotes the catabolism of unbound forms of vitamin E, showing stronger activity in non-alpha forms than in alpha. Because of these two opposing interactions, α T is preferentially accumulated in body tissues, whereas γ T and other forms of vitamin E are preferentially metabolized to hydroxycarboxychromanols, carboxychromanols, and their conjugated analogues. It is also worth mentioning that proteins that control absorption and excretion play an important role in bioavailability [7].

As it became clear from the above facts, α -TTP is the main reason for the difference in the concentration of α -, β -, γ -, δ -tocopherols and α -, β -, γ -, δ -tocotrienols. But in studies on mice and fruit flies without TTP, differences in concentrations still persisted (higher levels of α T than γ T in tissues) [8]. These observations suggested that enzymes of various forms of vitamin E may also be subject to selection by tocopherols and tocotrienols.

In addition to catabolism, another factor influencing the retention of these compounds in tissues is the excretion of vitamin E and its metabolites. Short-chain carboxychromanols and their sulfated or glucuronidated analogues are excreted in urine, while unconjugated carboxychromanols are mainly found in feces [9]. The work of Bardowell et al. [10] published in The Journal Biological Chemistry, it was found that approximately 80% of tocopherols and tocotrienols (metabolites) are excreted in the feces. Unchanged tocopherols and tocotrienols are also excreted in the bile (in the small intestine and feces).

Antioxidant activity: All isoforms of vitamin E have a powerful antioxidant effect due to the ability to scavenge lipid hydroperoxyl radicals by donating hydrogen from the phenolic group of the chromanol ring. Due to the presence of a phenolic ring, all forms of vitamin E are considered to have high antioxidant activity [1]. After a series of studies in 2001 and 2012, it was found that tocotrienols are better antioxidants than α T. This is due to the fact that tocotrienols are more evenly distributed on the lipid bilayer (phospholipid of the cell membrane), which provides a more effective interaction with hydroperoxyl radicals than tocopherols [11].

In addition to donating hydrogen, natural forms of vitamin E also have another way of disinfecting active form of nitrogen. So γ T has an unsubstituted position at 5 on the chromanol ring. During inflammatory reactions, NO_2 formed in large quantities joins precisely to this site, forming 5-nitro- γ T. But it must be taken into account that such a manifestation of antioxidant activity can be achieved only with the help of an unsubstituted part on the chromanol ring, and isoforms with a methyl group (α T) in the 5th position are not capable of this

[1,12]. This can be confirmed by experiments where an increase in 5-nitro- γ T was observed when peritonitis and occlusive thrombus were induced in rats.

Also, compared to α T, δ T and δ TE have higher antioxidant activity, preventing lipid peroxidation in vitro. Based on these statements, it is logical to assume that α T is less active than its analogues [13].

Anti-inflammatory and antitumor mechanisms of vitamin E: Chronic inflammation causes hyperreactivity to any flagogen. Such diseases can worsen the general well-being of the patient, can have serious consequences on the cardiovascular system and be a carcinogenic factor (the development of tumors) [2]. Inflammation is the result of the body's response to some kind of damage. During alteration, exudation and proliferation, a huge number of substances (inflammatory mediators) are synthesized, such as reactive oxygen/nitrogen species, prostaglandins, leukotrienes, cytokines, interleukins, etc. which, during strong inflammatory reactions, can even damage the tissues of the host itself [14].

Research has shown that certain forms of vitamin E, such as γ T, δ T, and tocotrienols (especially γ TE), have anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting COX-2 and 5-LOX (arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase). There is also evidence that some JAK-STAT6 and JAK-STAT3 signaling pathways can be blocked in various cell types. In addition, modified forms of vitamin E have been shown to be more active in inhibiting inflammation [7].

Animal experiments in clinical models have confirmed the beneficial effects of γ T and other forms of vitamin E in pathological conditions associated with inflammation and oxidative stress. Thus, such aspects as protection of the lungs from damage to their own aggressive factors, protection from tumorigenesis and colitis were studied. Some experiments may have conflicting results, which may be due to different routes of administration of vitamin E preparations [15].

A large number of studies aimed at revealing the essence of carcinogenesis have shown that inflammatory bowel diseases can dramatically increase the risk of tumorigenesis in this organ. It has become known that eicosanoids, COX and 5-LOX promote the development of cancer [16,17]. Due to its high antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, preparations containing vitamin E have been proposed as potentially useful chemopreventive agents against cancer. A 2009 study published in the journal Cancer Prevention Research suggested that drugs with high levels of all vitamin E isoforms, especially those rich in γ T, be prescribed as drug therapy [3]. The following results were presented as evidence: suppression of inflammation and tumorigenesis of the colon induced

by azoxymethane and dextrasulfate sodium in mice, representing an experimental model of colon cancer caused by colitis [3]; and the experiments of Jiang et al. showed that drugs with a high γ T content reduce the risk of oncogenesis of moderate colitis (caused after one cycle of sodium dextra sulfate administration), but not severe (more cycles of carcinogen administration) [32]. In addition to colon cancer, Sanchez et al. reported that a diet enriched with γ T reduces the risk of prostate epithelial dysplasia and hyperplasia [17].

The anti-inflammatory effects of not only tocopherols, but also tocotrienols have been demonstrated in various disease models. Thus, in the 2010 issue of the Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry [18], it was shown that under the influence of γ TE, but not α T, they suppress the formation of prostaglandins E2 and cytokines under the influence of UV-B. This is achieved by blocking the pro-inflammatory transmission of keratinocytes and inducing COX-2. Also, in experiments on mice, it was shown that tocotrienols increase the proliferation of lymphocytes [19]. In CD2F1 mice, subcutaneous injection of δ TE dramatically reduced radiation-induced mortality and promoted bone marrow and stem cell regeneration. This protective effect is most likely due to kinase activation coupled to extracellular signals. Tsuduki et al. [20] reported that foods rich in γ TE reduced the clinical manifestations of allergic dermatitis in mice by suppressing degranulation and histamine secretion in mast cells. Also, palm oil rich in tocotrienol softens the course of chronic pancreatitis and protects kidney damage associated with potassium dichromate. It is worth mentioning that studies have confirmed the effect of α T, δ TE and mixed tocotrienols on the immunization of mice against tetanus toxoid. These isoforms of vitamin E are able to enhance the production of antibodies against the toxin.

CONCLUSION

According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer, in 2020-2021 the number of new cases of cancer increased to 19.3 million people, and mortality among them to 10 million. Such high figures can be associated with a serious blow by country and citizen due to the pandemic, which may have led to a decline in quality of life. And also, with an increase in the amount of hazardous waste. But the fact remains unknown. Cancer is on the rise worldwide. Based on this, doctors, medical students and other medical professionals should promote a healthy lifestyle. In particular, everyone should know which products contain certain useful substances in what quantities and how they can be useful. The evidence presented in this review indicates that in experiments with changes in diet, i.e. consuming more tocopherols and tocotrienols reduces the high

reactivity of the body and further blocks the carcinogenic effect of inflammatory reactions in the human body.

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